

Research paper

A 3D geological model of El Hierro volcanic island reflecting intraplate volcanism cycles

Alejandro García-Gil^{a,*}, Carlos Baquedano^a, Miguel Ángel Marazuela^{a,*}, Jorge Martínez-León^a, Noelia Cruz-Pérez^b, Luis E. Hernández-Gutiérrez^b, Juan C. Santamarta^b

^a Geological Survey of Spain (IGME-CSIC). C/ Ríos Rosas 23, 28003 Madrid. Spain

^b Departamento de Ingeniería Agraria y del Medio Natural. Universidad de La Laguna (ULL), La Laguna (Tenerife). C/ Pedro Herrera, s/n, 38200, San Cristóbal de La Laguna. Spain

HIGHLIGHTS

- The 3D geology of El Hierro (Canary islands) was investigated.
- A methodology to build a 3D geological model of volcanic islands was proposed.
- Volcanic activity cycles were related to volcanic units geometry.
- New variables to investigate rift zones and giant lateral collapses were examined.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

3D geological model
El Hierro island
Canary islands
Rift zones
Giant landslides

ABSTRACT

Fully 3D and multidimensional geological models are key for energy, mining and water resources assessment and management, which has a great economic impact. 3D geological models provide critical information regarding geometric properties of the geological bodies of interest, such as ore deposits or reservoirs, allowing inference of volumes and availability to be exploited. However, defining a useful methodology to create a fully digital 3D geological model of volcanic islands is still very challenging due to the intrinsic complexity observed in the structure of volcanic systems. Two-dimensional geological maps, associated vertical geological cross-sectional diagrams and borehole and water-mining tunnels (galleries) logs were examined on *El Hierro* Island. A geological modelling procedure using the software GeoModeller obtained the first 3D geological model of *El Hierro* volcanic island, as a basis for volcanic formation definitions and geometric analysis. Surface, volume and center of mass estimations of the differentiated sub-units allowed a better understanding of the spatial distribution and evolution of the volcanic cycles of *El Hierro* Island over time. The 3D model provided geometry information correlatable with volcanic activity cycles and lava/pyroclast deposition mechanisms that ultimately defines the geometry of the volcanic units. This information provides new variables valuable for the investigation of the existing relationships between rift zones and giant lateral collapses. In addition, the obtained 3D geological model of a volcanic island will support the building of the first hydrogeological and geothermal model of *El Hierro* Island, allowing advancement of sustainability of isolated systems.

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: a.garcia@igme.es (A. García-Gil), ma.marazuela@igme.es (M.Á. Marazuela).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2023.100936>

Received 20 January 2023; Received in revised form 18 February 2023; Accepted 4 March 2023

Available online 9 March 2023

2352-801X/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Groundwater is the largest unfrozen freshwater reservoir on Earth underpinning human development and important ecosystems (Eamus et al., 2016; Gleeson et al., 2020). It supplies approximately two billion people with drinking water worldwide (Morris et al., 2003) and satisfies 40% of the global irrigation demand (Siebert et al., 2010). Groundwater resources in arid and semi-arid regions are suffering from depletion due to increasing demands and limited recharge rates (Scanlon et al., 2006). In these regions, where surface water resources are scarce or absent, islanders are forced to rely up to 95% on groundwater resources to provide fresh water for human consumption, agriculture and livestock (Duncan, 2012). This combination of factors is what has made efficient management of freshwater resources and policy establishment a major challenge for the authorities of these islands (Tribble, 2008; White and Falkland, 2010). Furthermore, heterogeneity and anisotropy in volcanic oceanic islands have been recognized as major factors conditioning resource assessment and planning (Custodio et al., 2016; Santamarta et al., 2014). Although most volcanic rock formations are considered poorly permeable, productive aquifers can be found in Quaternary volcanic rocks when an alternation of fissured lavas and porous pyroclasts are found (Margat and Van der Gun, 2013). Volcanic formations possess characteristic geometries compared with sedimentary deposits,

due to the endogenous processes which generate them: solidification of magma/lava and pyroclastic deposition. These volcanic structures developed in volcanic zones are linked to lava composition and type of eruption, thus, conditioning groundwater flow regimes (Singhal and Gupta, 2010). Significant volcanic structures that condition groundwater flow in volcanic islands include extensive layering produced by successive eruptions, dykes extending several kilometres, volcanic edifices, submarine basalts and massive landslides (Custodio, 2020). The central part of volcanic islands is characterized by a swarm of vertical dykes (low permeability), cutting across the lava flows and acting as barriers against groundwater flow towards the sea, thereby forming water compartments at different heights (Lachassagne et al., 2014). Therefore, the heterogeneity inherent to volcanic island geology is required to understand groundwater flow in such environments. In particular, these heterogeneities have been considered critical in hydrogeological studies of volcanic islands worldwide; in the Atlantic Ocean, including the Macaronesia archipelagos such as Azores (García-Gil et al., 2022), Madeira (Prada et al., 2005), Canary Islands (García-Gil et al., 2022), Cape Verde (Lopes et al., 2022) and the Lesser Antilles (Hemmings et al., 2015); in the Pacific Ocean, such as the Hawaiian Islands (Lachassagne et al., 2014), the Galapagos Islands (Violette et al., 2014) and most of the islands of Oceania (Hughes et al., 2022); and in the Indian Ocean in islands such as Comoros (Comte et al.,

Fig. 1. Geographical location of the study area. Cartographic base obtained from the Territorial Information System of the Canary Islands. Projection: REGCAN95 UTM Zone 28 N. Modified from Troll and Carracedo (2016) and IGME (IGME, 1997a; IGME, 1997b; IGME, 1997c; IGME, 1997d).

Fig. 2. Representative cross-sections of El Hierro volcanic island. Modified from Troll and Carracedo (2016) and IGME (IGME, 1997a; IGME, 1997b; IGME, 1997c; IGME, 1997d).

2016), Reunion (Join et al., 2016) and Mauritius (Povinec et al., 2012). Hydrogeological characterization of volcanic aquifers in oceanic islands requires sophisticated technical and methodological instruments including the use of remote sensors (El-Rayes et al., 2020), specific mathematical models (Herrera and Custodio, 2014) and geostatistical methods derived from pseudo-regional hydraulic tests (Poncela et al., 2022). Historically, hydrogeologists have coped with heterogeneity in natural porous media using spatially-distributed numerical modelling (Anderson et al., 2015). Distributed models can be valuable tools because they have the ability to take the subsurface heterogeneity into account and provide distributed output variables (Dehotin and Braud, 2008). However, spatially distributed models require 3D geological models to provide spatial discretization of the numerical model domain, thus accounting for existing heterogeneities. Numerical models in hydrogeology have progressively incorporated 3D geological models for the evaluation of groundwater capacity and vulnerability, to depict aquifers and their properties at local, regional, or national scales (MacCormack et al., 2019; Turner et al., 2021). Using 3D geological modelling as a basis for hydrogeological research in volcanic environments has been proven to provide a significant improvement of groundwater resource assessments, as it allows reducing geometry and parametrization uncertainty of the aquifers (Gill et al., 2011). Although the geology of volcanoes has been extensively researched in previous works (Bonforte et al., 2022; Cas et al., 2018; Macdonald et al., 1983; Schmincke, 2004), references on 3D geological model building are scarce and limited to the island of Weh, to our knowledge (Nugraha and O’Sullivan, 2019). Weh is a young volcanic island located in the northern part of the Great Sumatra Fault system (Indonesia). The

authors developed a 3D geological model with the commercial software LEAPFROG to define a geothermal reservoir of the *Jaboi* geothermal area. The obtained geological model resulted to be a very useful 3D visualization tool and compiled all of the geological and geothermal exploration data obtained to date: geological structures, rock types, water level, and surface manifestations.

In this paper, we present the first 3D geological model of *El Hierro* volcanic island, as a basis for hydrogeological and geothermal research. The main objective of this work is to propose and apply a methodology to build a fully digital 3D geological model of the volcanic island, consistent with a 20-year-old set of paper geological maps by the Geological Survey of Spain (IGME-CSIC) and other datasets described below. The second objective of this work is to provide suitable metadata about the 3D geological model of *El Hierro* Island, making it available to potential users and informing them about its specifications and its uncertainties. The methodology presented to develop a 3D geological model of volcanic islands will support the building of the first hydrogeological and geothermal model of *El Hierro* Island. This will allow reproduction of groundwater flow and transport processes of solutes and heat at an insular scale. The simulations obtained from this model will improve the hydrogeological knowledge of this volcanic island and thus advance knowledge about aquifer vulnerability in volcanic islands, in addition to creating strategies for adaptation to climate change. Reproducing heat transport in the subsurface will allow to investigate the shallow geothermal potential and its renewability due to groundwater advection of heat will be investigated.

2. Study area

The Canary Islands archipelago is the emerged part of the Canary Volcanic Province, which is composed of seven main islands and several islets as well as the associated seamounts. The archipelago is found in the Eastern Atlantic Ocean region (28° N, 16° W); 100 km from the African coast (Fig. 1). The island of *El Hierro* is the youngest, most western and southern island of the Canary Archipelago. It has a total emerged area of 268.7 km² and a maximum altitude of 1501 m a.s.l. (meters above mean sea level). A total of 58% of its surface is environmentally protected and, in 2000, the whole island became a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. In addition, the entire island of *El Hierro* was also classed as a UNESCO Global Geopark in 2014. A very characteristic morphological feature of oceanic volcanic islands is its shape, a truncated triangular pyramid with three alignments corresponding to a classic 120° spaced volcanic rift system, coalescing in its central sector, where it reaches its maximum altitude (island summit). Without a doubt, the most outstanding geological relief on the island is the impressive *El Golfo* valley, officially recognized as one of the Global Geosites (IGME, 2022). It originated almost instantly after the mobilization of some 180 km³ of the northern flank of the island, both in its subaerial and submarine portion, producing a 14.5 km wide depression, limited by a semi-circular escarpment, which has a maximum height of 1100 m in its central sector. The hydrogeology of *El Hierro* and its groundwater supply systems have been extensively studied by [Santamarta \(2017\)](#) and [Santamarta and Rodríguez-Martín \(2020\)](#), describing the geological structures involved in the movement and storage of water in the island aquifer, comparing it with the Hawaiian Islands.

The oldest subaerial rocks of *El Hierro* are dated at 1.12 Myr ([Guillou et al., 1996](#)) and the geology is representative of a volcanic oceanic island in its initial phase of shield development. Most of the island is covered by cinder cones and recent lava flows, as surface expressions of emission vents fed by aligned dyke swarms. The steep topographic hillsides are scarcely affected by erosive gullies. The internal structure of the island is formed by overlapping volcanic edifices that successively developed and collapsed. The collapses of the volcanic edifices are caused by giant landslides located between volcanic rift arms, resulting in horseshoe-shaped embayments ([Troll and Carracedo, 2016](#)).

Based on stratigraphic and radiometric data ([Abdel-Monem et al., 1972](#); [Guillou et al., 1996](#); [Perez-Torrado et al., 2011](#)), three large superimposed volcanoes have been identified as result of subaerial activity in the island: the *Tiñor*, the *El Golfo*, and the recent Rift volcano (Fig. 1).

The *Tiñor* volcano (1.12–0.88 Myr) is the first subaerial volcanic edifice, and its outcrops are found in the northeast part of the island as well as the *Las Playas* inlet. Three main construction phases have been distinguished, defining three lithological sub-units (Fig. 1): the lower section, the tabular section, and the *Ventejís* volcanic group. While the first two phases correspond to fluid lavas transitioning from steeply dipping to sub-horizontal flows, the third phase corresponds to the most explosive activity stage of the edifice, presenting emission vents with well-preserved wide craters ([Troll and Carracedo, 2016](#)). The lower and tabular sections are constituted by alkaline basaltic emissions, intensely affected by phyllonian rocks and alternating with intercalated pyroclastic levels (lapilli and volcanic slag). The latter intercalations increase towards the end of the lithostratigraphic unit in the *Ventejís* area, where a complex stratovolcano is observed ([IGME, 1997a](#)). The *Tiñor* edifice growth was rapid and uninterrupted; this is characteristic of the first stages of any volcanic island development and it typically results in major flank instability due to accompaniment by magmatic and pore fluid pressurisation, triggered by the dyke emplacement ([Elsworth and Voight, 1995](#)). The *Tiñor* volcano cycle ended with a giant landslide, where the western flank of the *Tiñor* edifice collapsed. Currently, the associated landslide scar is hidden by the subsequent emissions of the *El Golfo* edifice and by the volcanism of the Rifts (Fig. 2A, cross-section 1 and Fig. 2B, cross-section 2).

The *El Golfo* edifice (545–175 kyr) arose approximately 350 kyr after the western flank of the *Tiñor* edifice collapsed. It developed entirely in the Brunhes epoch, nestled in the slide of the *Tiñor* edifice, forming an angular unconformity that overlaps the remains of the *Tiñor* volcano, thus extending the island to the west. Morphological differences and local unconformities in the *El Golfo* volcanic edifice allow identification of three sub-units (Fig. 1): the lower section, the upper-middle section and the upper section. The lower section is mainly composed of strombolian pyroclasts, with subordinate presence of basaltic lava flows, materials related to explosive eruptions with surtseyan cinder cones and tuff rings. This section is cut by northeast, east-south-east, and west-northwest trending dyke swarms, which also configure the current volcanic vent systems. The upper-middle section of the *El Golfo* edifice shows no clear discordance with the lower section, indicating continuous emission. The materials of the upper-middle section also include basaltic lava flows but, in this case, with less dense dyke swarms and the presence of subordinated pyroclastic cones ([IGME, 1997a](#)). The upper section of the *El Golfo* edifice consists of different block-and-ash deposits (trachybasalts, trachytes) and differentiated lava flows, which probably represents the last stages of the volcanic activity ([Troll and Carracedo, 2016](#)). During the final stages of the *El Golfo* edifice construction, a giant landslide occurred (176 kyr) in the SW sector ([IGME, 1997c](#)). This is evidenced by a wide arc formed in the SW sector of the island, the absence of the *El Golfo* materials and the large pile of lavas released during the later ridge volcanism in the *El Julian* area (Fig. 2D, cross-section 4). Furthermore, the study carried out on the continental shelf by [Holcomb and Searle \(1991\)](#) shows the existence of avalanche deposits on the seafloor.

The third and last main volcano edifice of the island involves the recent rift volcanism (<158 kyr), which is made up of rift series lavas as the last volcanic stage in the island's growth. It consists of strombolian cones located along the three arms of the rift, resulting from simultaneous activity and lava emissions that cover the two previous volcano edifices. The recent rift volcanism is the unit that occupies the largest area of the island. It consists of basaltic lava flows that are mainly located over the *El Golfo* edifice ([IGME, 1997b](#)). In the final eruptive phases of the rift volcanism, during the Upper Pleistocene, the ascending magma injection thrust into the upper part of the island produced a severe lithostatic breakdown. This led to the destabilization and collapse of the *El Golfo* edifice, including the overlapping lava flows of the volcanism of the ridges, generating a large horseshoe-shaped embayment between the northern and western rift arms ([IGME, 1997c](#); [Mancini et al., 2009](#)). This giant landslide profoundly altered the physiognomy of the island and is the most important morphological feature of *El Hierro* (Fig. 2C, cross-section 3). The collapse scar starts at an altitude of 1500 m. a.s.l and ends up at 3200 m. a.s.l., and the mobilized materials are deposited 65 km off the coastline of the island, covering 1500 km² of seafloor ([Masson et al., 2002](#); [Troll and Carracedo, 2016](#)). Coetaneous to this event, another landslide took place in the eastern part of the island, affecting the *Las Playas* section ([Gee et al., 2001](#); [Masson et al., 2002](#)). The subsequent erosive action on the escarpment generated a large volume of detrital deposits at its base.

After the landslide at the *El Golfo* area (not the volcano), different lava flows filled the formed depression, whose emission centers were located on the steep slopes of the depression, close to or within the structural axis, where the greatest eruptive activity was concentrated at that time. This volcanism was dominantly effusive, with massive lava emissions that flowed towards the coastline, filling the valley and reaching a thickness of 300 m in some places ([IGME, 1997c](#)). At the same time, at the ends of the rift arms, there were emissions of lava flows that overflowed the paleo-cliffs of the *Tiñor* and *El Golfo* edifices, giving rise to small coastal platforms called *low islands*. These emissions have been assigned to sub-recent and recent times and illustrate the continuous growth of the island around the structural axes ([IGME, 1997a](#); [IGME, 1997b](#)).

Recent sedimentary materials include colluvium deposits, consisting

Fig. 3. Definition of the four primary sources used for building the 3D geological model of El Hierro volcanic island: Digital Terrain Model (DTM), surface geological maps, vertical geological cross-sectional diagrams, and borehole and gallery input data.

of coarse detrital materials, angular blocks, cobbles and sands. These materials are mostly associated with the *Las Playas* and *El Golfo* escarpments, located at the foot of these basaltic reliefs (IGME, 1997c).

Regarding the island's hydrogeology (IGME, 1997c; Troll and Carracedo, 2016), the materials belonging to the *Tiñor* edifice are made up of hard rocks of low permeability, which have a low hydraulic conductivity and low storativity. However, these hard rocks are affected by a dense dyke swarm, comprising fractured rocks that may show moderate to good secondary permeability, depending on the fracturing degree, and thus presenting high anisotropy. The materials corresponding to *El Golfo* volcano edifice present a high permeability, due to their favourable low degree of alteration and compaction, and they constitute the main aquifer of the island. The materials associated with the activity in the Rifts that correspond to the volcanism of the ridges, the volcanism at *El Golfo* area and the sub-recent and recent emissions have not undergone alteration and will also tend to present high permeability.

3. Methodology

3.1. Input data for the El Hierro 3D geological model

The datasets on geological information of *El Hierro* Island are mainly available as 2D maps and associated vertical geological cross-sectional diagrams, and borehole water-mining tunnels (galleries) logs (Fig. 3). Most of this dataset proceeds from petrological, geochronological (Abdel-Monem et al., 1972; Fúster et al., 1993) and palaeomagnetic data (Guillou et al., 1996; Szérméta et al., 1999). The data was obtained from geological sections showing the collapse scars and deep gullies; the wells, boreholes and water-mining tunnel geological profiles in *El Golfo*; and the recent rift volcanoes. Concretely, to build the presented 3D geological model of *El Hierro*, a total of five geological maps, four 20-year-old sets of paper geological maps at 1:25,000 scale from the Spanish Geological Survey (IGME, 1997a; IGME, 1997b; IGME, 1997c; IGME, 1997d), and one from Troll and Carracedo (2016) were considered. The documentation associated with these maps included seven and

Fig. 4. Three main workflows processing surface geological (A) vertical cross-sections (B) borehole and gallery input data into fully 3D geological model. Georeferenced input features (top) extracted from the surface maps, vertical cross-sections and borehole and gallery data imported into the GeoModeller interface (middle) and results obtained from the 3D interpolation.

five cross-sections respectively, which were also used for building the 3D model (Figs. 2G and 3). In addition, lithological profile descriptions of 15,773 m from 37 waterworks and boreholes were used as input in the 3D model (Fig. 3). Those included two high-diameter (>5 m) canary wells (213 m total perforation), 14 boreholes (2047 m), 10 galleries (8139 m) and 11 well-galleries (5.374 m). In the Canary Islands, it is typical to find high-diameter wells that go deep vertically (or with a given angle) until the perforation reaches the groundwater level, and then the drilling turns horizontal or dips to low angles (<5°). All the direction changes and inclinations of the galleries and well-galleries are available and described in the 3D geological model (Fig. 3C).

The fourth primary source used to create the 3D geological model was the Digital Terrain Model (DTM). The DTMs obtained from the Spain National Geographic Institute (IGN) were created from the LIDAR point cloud, with a density of 0.5 points per square meter with a Root-Mean-Square Error (RMSE) in the z axis under 0.20 m (1 sigma) (CNIG, 2020). They consisted in a raster dataset with a horizontal cell resolution of 25 m, and represented the land surface without any vegetation or buildings.

3.2. “El Hierro” 3D geological model workflow

The workflow for building the 3D geological model of *El Hierro* was initiated once all available input data (existing and new data) were collected and processed (Fig. 3) by data compilation in the GeoModeller software platform (Gibson et al., 2013). This software makes use of the implicit geological modelling approach for the modelling of complex geological structures. The code uses geological observations and/or

cartographic data to generate 3-D geological surfaces and volumes. Specifically, it incorporates an algorithm (Calcagno et al., 2008; Lajouanie et al., 1997) which applies cokriging to geological interfaces and orientation data obtained from structural fields to interpolate a continuous 3D potential field scalar function describing both the geology and geometry. The software uses its own concept of *geological pile* to allow the aggregation of these boundaries and maintain stratigraphic relationships and fault network chronology. The definition of a geological pile involves a given topology of the interfaces to characterize their spatial architecture without considering their chronological order. After defining the fault geometry with specific potential fields, the software calculates fault displacements from universal kriging calculations of the discontinuities. Finally, the defined geological pile establishes spatial relationships between each individual model of each series to complete the 3-D model.

The geologic modelling procedure inside the GeoModeller environment is synthesized in the following steps. First, a resolution of 10 m was adopted for the model and its domain was set by a bounding box of $29 \times 25 \times 6$ km, containing the whole island down to 3000 m.b.m.s.l. (meters below mean sea level). Then, the DTM was prepared and imported into GeoModeller to characterize the upper surface of the geological model. After that, the geological pile was defined to accomplish its modelling. Considering that the objective of the 3D geological model is to address groundwater management and geothermal potential estimations, this project targeted the mapping of different hydrostratigraphic units to discretize rock porosity and permeability distributions. The sequence of lithological formations to be created included the volcanic materials that allowed description and interpretation of the main three volcanos.

Table 1

Resulted geometrical parameters of the geological pile units constituting the 3D geological model of *El Hierro* Island. Coordinates projection: REGCAN95 UTM Zone 28 N. Volumes and areas computed considered the model domain between the island summits (1501 m.a.s.l.) to -120 m.a.s.l.

Geological Pile		Surface		Volume		Surf./Vol ratio.	Center of Mass		
Units	Sub-units	[km ²]	%	[km ³]	%	[-]	x	y	z
							[m]	[m]	[m a.s.l.]
Rifts	<i>Recent emissions</i>	28.94	10.76	1.47	0.63	0.06	203005	3070205	181
	<i>Subrecent emissions</i>	10.22	3.80	0.32	0.14	0.04	209511	3074813	586
	<i>Volcanism of El Golfo</i>	42.15	15.67	29.32	12.60	0.80	200501	3073922	241
	<i>Sediments</i>	2.04	0.76	0.17	0.07	0.10	208735	3070324	77
	<i>Ridge volcanism</i>	182.48	67.84	40.11	17.19	0.25	203032	3071603	510
El Golfo Edifice	<i>Upper sec. (trachytes)</i>	31.49	11.71	1.44	0.62	0.05	206942	3075144	838
	<i>Upper-middle section</i>	141.67	52.66	51.76	22.25	0.42	202614	3070771	426
	<i>Lower section</i>	152.49	56.69	69.26	29.77	0.53	200799	3071822	144
Tiñor Edifice	<i>Ventejís Volcano</i>	20.17	7.50	4.87	2.09	0.09	212338	3,079,224	423
	<i>Tabular section</i>	62.75	23.33	14.61	6.28	0.27	209780	3075260	324
	<i>Lower section</i>	97.43	36.22	19.46	8.36	0.23	210135	3075879	36

This geological pile allowed inclusion of mapping units and relevant known structures in a generalized geological model. The different formation classification schemes used in each separate geological map sheet covered all the island and its harmonization to obtain at a single sequence. The result of this harmonization is the units and sub-units shown in Fig. 1. The geological pile definition was followed by preparation of surface geological data. The maps were obtained in digital format (Fig. 4A). The geological maps were georeferenced and then

imported into GeoModeller to manually digitalize the formation interfaces of the geological pile intersecting the topography, orientation data, and faults.

The vertical pre-existing cross-sections found in the literature and described above were edited to distinguish subsurface interfaces and orientations of the units defined in the geological pile of GeoModeller (Fig. 2). The adapted vertical cross-section diagrams were cut and the start and end locations for the cross-section were georeferenced before

Fig. 5. Obtained fully 3D geological model of *El Hierro* Island. (A) 3D projected cross-sections with opaque surfaces for the geological sub-units and transparent for the water body, in (B) 3D wireframe view, and (C) as a fence diagram.

Fig. 6. Geometry of the geological sub-units inside *El Hierro* Island according to its geological history. (A) *Tiñor* Edifice Volcano, (B) *El Golfo* Edifice Volcano and (D and E) Rifts final stage.

Fig. 7. Spatial and time change of center of mass of the main geological sub-units of *El Hierro* Island. (A–C) *Tiñor* edifice and (D–F) *El Golfo-Rifts* cycles are differentiated. (G) Time evolution of the coordinates changes of center of mass of the main geological sub-units.

being imported into GeoModeller (Fig. 4B). The cross-sections provided interpretations of the three main volcano edifices, including the pronounced faulting related to giant landslides. Once imported, the correspondence between each topographic surface profile calculated by GeoModeller and the topography represented on the georeferenced cross-section was verified. The 12 cross-sections extracted from the literature (Fig. 2G) and adapted for the 3D model were distributed throughout the domain. The next step was 3D projection of all borehole,

well and gallery geological profiles/logs (Fig. 4C). These projections identifying the defined geological pile units were correlated by making use of 59 additional auxiliary cross-sections (Fig. 2G) that ensured a fully 3D model interpolation robustness. The final task before computing the 3D model consisted of checking, through exhaustive 3D visualization, the consistency between all surface and subsurface interface and orientation points, borehole and gallery projections to be 3D-interpolated.

3.3. Geometric analysis of El Hierro main 3D geological units

The obtained 3D geological model results for every sub-unit were exported in the form of a 40×40 m horizontal (x, y) grid data framework. To understand the distribution of mass in the geological units, the exported data set were used to calculate the center of mass of each subunit according to:

$$R(x_R, y_R, z_R) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^n m_i r(x_i, y_i, z_i) \quad (1)$$

where R is the position vector of the center of mass with coordinates x_R, y_R, z_R , r is the position vector of the i -th particle in the geological sub-units of n particles, m_i is the mass of the i -th particle and M is the total mass of the particles, which was assumed constant since a density distribution map of the subunits was not available. Although giant landslides have affected the main volcano edifices of the island, the centers of mass were calculated to evaluate possible similitudes and differences between geological bodies and discuss possible emission points of the volcanic materials.

In addition to centers of masses, the slope distribution for each top shell of the different geological subunits was calculated. This was calculated in the *ArcMap 10* (ESRI, 2011) environment. The coordinate of the top shell points of each subunit was converted into rasters to run the *slope* tool (Spatial Analyst), which allowed identification of the steepness at each cell of a raster surface, calculated using the average maximum technique (Burrough et al., 2015).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. 3D geological model and historical evolution of El Hierro volcanic island

A resume of the main geometrical parameters of the obtained 3D reconstruction of *El Hierro* Island is shown in Table 1. The most spread materials are those related to the ridge volcanism, with an extension of 182.5 km^2 (67.8% of the island surface), followed by *El Golfo* lower and middle sub-units, with 152.5 and 141.7 km^2 , respectively (56.7 and 52.7% respectively). The *Tiñor* edifice's sub-units presented three to two times smaller than the ridge volcanism. In terms of volume, the middle and lower sub-units of the *El Golfo* edifice presented the largest values of 69.3 and 51.8 km^3 , representing 52.0% of the emerged island volume. The following 29.8% of the emerged volume is mainly constituted by *Rifts* materials associated with ridge volcanism (40.1 km^3) and volcanism of *El Golfo* (29.3 km^3) sub-units. An additional 16.7% of the emerged volume is constituted by the *Tiñor* edifice sub-units. In total, the accumulated volume in all these described sub-units accounts for 98.5% of the merged volume of the island. The surface/volume ratio showed a clear cyclicity along the material stacking at the main volcano edifices of *Tiñor* and *El Golfo*. In the first stages, the ratio was relatively large (0.23–0.53), and this drastically decreased to 0.05–0.09 in the last stages of volcanic activity of the main edifices. In the last *Rifts* cycle stages, where mapped lava flow materials are shallow and local, similar ratios below 0.10 were observed. The obtained fully 3D geological model is shown in Fig. 5A, as 3D projected with opaque surfaces in geological sub-units and transparent for the water body. Fig. 5B presents the 3D wireframe view and Fig. 5C as a fence diagram, with some cross-sections intersecting the most important borehole and water gallery geological profiles.

The geometry of the geological sub-units inside the island can be described according to the geological history of the island (Fig. 6). The first main volcano edifice (*Tiñor*), after its collapse and before *Las Playas* landslide, is shown in Fig. 6A. The paleorelief of the *Tiñor* edifice was actuated as an underpin surface for the subsequent *El Golfo* lava flows of the lower and middle sections. The *El Golfo* edifice is believed to have developed a 20 km-diameter volcanic shield (Custodio, 2020) before its

multiple collapses through three major landslides: *El Golfo*, *El Julian* and *Las Playas* landslides. The geological model allowed to fully 3D reconstruct its geometries (Fig. 6B). Thanks to the 3D geological model, and according to Table 1, after its collapse, the *El Golfo* edifice still represented 52.6% of the emerged island volume, which is 3.1 times the *Tiñor* edifice. Fig. 6C shows the ridge volcanism sub-unit, which was also affected by the later landslides. This figure also shows how the stacking of these sub-units configures the final scar of the giant landslide that destroyed the largest volcanic shield of the island to date, and the circumstances previous to the volcanism of *El Golfo* was emplaced in the decompressed area (Fig. 6D). Finally, Fig. 6E shows the recent and sub-recent lava flow emissions, together with minor sedimentary deposits.

4.2. Unravelling volcanism cycles from the 3D geological model of the El Hierro Island

The calculated center of mass of each geological sub-unit identified in the 3D geological model is shown in Table 1. The elevation (z coordinate) of the center of mass of the sub-units clearly shows the staking evolution within the major volcanic cycles, with a positive increase of 99–412 m after the major collapse of each edifice. The total accumulated increase of each edifice was 387, 694 and 509 m for the *Tiñor*, *El Golfo* and *Rifts* edifices, respectively. The spatial descriptions of center of mass of the main sub-units are shown in Fig. 7. The spatial changes of the center of mass of the *Tiñor* edifice sub-units show a clear linear 5 km drift NE, with a 39° eastward deviation from the north (Fig. 7A). In addition, vertical profiles in Fig. 7B and C show how the mass center of mass of the lower and tabular sub-units presents similar horizontal coordinates, while the center of mass of the *Ventejís* sub-unit increases those coordinates.

The rest of the centers of mass of the main geological sub-units of the *El Golfo* and *Rifts* edifices are concentrated towards the west, close to the three rift arms coalescence, where the major elevations of the island are found. Differences among the centers of mass of these sub-units (Fig. 7D) can be explained by the main *El Golfo* landslide scar concave morphology, which similarly affected the ridge volcanism and upper-middle sub-units (vertical fault plane), but not the lower section (low-angle fault plane). Fig. 7E shows a linear dependency of the center of mass with respect to the x coordinate, including the ridge volcanism sub-unit. Although this sub-unit is considered to be part of another volcanic cycle (*Rifts* edifice), its geometry suggests a close relationship with the *El Golfo* cycle.

The alignment of the centers of mass of the *Tiñor* edifice geological units is consistent with the NE ridge arm of the island, thus suggesting that *El Hierro* was initially a single-rift system. This is consistent with the general growth model of volcanic islands (Fiske and Jackson, 1972). The geological model suggests that, in the first stages of island growth, the volcanic edifice did not grow along the three-armed configuration (Becerril et al., 2015). The collapse of the *Tiñor* edifice seems to represent the opening of the eastern and southern ridge arm, thus adopting the current 120° three-armed configuration. This would explain the greater extension of the largest volcanic shield developed during the *El Golfo* cycle.

Finally, the temporal evolution of center of mass coordinate changes of the main geological sub-units is shown in Fig. 7G. This figure clearly shows the fluctuation in elevation and the horizontal coordinate changes over time in a logarithmic scale (base 10). Although increments change solidary between them, elevation is clearly less affected (one order of magnitude lower). The cause of this fluctuation cannot be clearly identified and is only speculated upon, with the stacking of the volcanic materials and maybe fluctuations of the hot-spot relative position. The lack of increments change solidary between the x -coordinate and the rest of them, which could be related to a southern displacement of the volcanic activity towards the southern ridge arm, corroborated by the last eruption episode in *La Restinga* (Jurado et al., 2020) and offshore

Fig. 8. (A) Spatial distribution of sloping apron of the top surface for each main sub-unit in *El Hierro* Island. (B) Spatial correlation between sloping aprons of the upper-middle section of *El Golfo* edifice and the Ridge volcanism subunit. (C) Boxplot diagram of the sloping aprons of main sub-units in *El Hierro* Island. Outliers and extremes are represented by circles and asterisks, respectively.

ridge mapping (Gee et al., 2001). This southern migration of the volcanic activity has also been observed in *La Palma* Island, close to *El Hierro* Island in space and time development (Carracedo et al., 2001).

The 3D geological model of *El Hierro* Island allowed investigation of spatial distribution of the sloping aprons of the top surfaces of the main sub-units (Fig. 8A). The slopes are clearly conditioned by the giant landslides, where slopes present values between 16 and 35° on average, and up to 39°, 37° and 23° in the Lower, Tabular and *Ventejis* sub-units, respectively, of the *Tiñor* edifice. Aside from the landslide scars, each sub-unit presents a different spatial distribution. However, the upper-middle section (*El Golfo* edifice) and Ridge volcanism (*Rifts* edifice) present a very similar pattern. The Pearson coefficient indicates a positive correlation (Fig. 8B) with a variation of slopes between these sub-units in 34% of the evaluated slopes ($n = 300$). Boxplot diagrams of the sloping aprons of the main sub-units (Fig. 8C) indicate a cyclicity of the volcanic activity in the island. The median slopes in the lower section of the cycles goes from 10.0° (*Tiñor* edifice) down to 9.2° in the middle section and rises up again at the end of the cycle in the *Ventejis* sub-unit. This cycle in the sloping aprons is reinitiated in the lower section (*El Golfo* edifice) and apparently finishes with the Ridge volcanism sub-unit, thus including the *Rifts* edifice. Under this interpretation, the volcanism of the *El Golfo* sub-unit would correspond to the start of a new cycle, i.e., the first stages of a new edifice. The lower slopes could be related to lava flows of a fluid nature with low angles of deposition, the lower the viscosity, the lower the slope. The deposition of pyroclasts will tend to present higher slopes with respect to the local domain. Therefore, analysis of the slopes could help to infer the disposition genesis.

5. Conclusions

The presented 3D geological model of *El Hierro* volcanic island defined a useful methodology to build fully digital 3D geological models of volcanic islands and is the first model of *El Hierro* Island. In addition, the proposed methodology provides a valuable geometrical insight of the volcano-stratigraphic units. These units can help to better understand volcanic activity cycles that, in the end, constrain its heterogeneity and, subsequently, groundwater flow and water resources availability. The 3D geological model allowed the spatial description of the centers of mass of the main sub-units of the *Tiñor* edifice, suggesting that *El Hierro* was initially a single-rift system. The distribution of these centers of mass in the *Tiñor* edifice contrasted with those of the *El Golfo* and *Rifts* edifice sub-units, which were found to concentrate at the coalescence of the three rift arms. This suggests that the collapse of the *Tiñor* edifice was followed by the opening of the eastern and southern ridge arm that configures the current 120° three-armed morphology. This opening of the three rift arms would explain the greater extension of the largest volcanic shield developed during the *El Golfo* cycle. Moreover, the spatio-temporal analysis of the centers of mass showed a cyclic pattern of the main geological sub-units where fluctuations in elevation and lateral displacements over time were found to coincide with the main volcanic cycles associated with volcanic edifice stacking. Finally, the spatial and temporal-distribution analysis of the sloping aprons of the top surfaces in each main sub-unit were found to be clearly conditioned by giant landslides and volcanic activity cycles of the island, respectively.

The 3D information provided by the 3D geological model provides new variables to study the relationships between rift zones and giant lateral collapses. The 3D model is expected to serve as a basis for the first hydrogeological and geothermal model of *El Hierro* Island, thus allowing reproduction of groundwater flow and heat transport processes at an insular scale. This will improve the hydrogeological and geothermal knowledge of this volcanic island, thus advancing renewable resource management, which is of great importance in remote islands with scarce water resources and a dependency on energy importation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This research was partially supported by the SAGE4CAN project, which is funded by the Spanish Research Agency (AEI project PID2020-114218RA-I00), and the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (project ARSINOE 101037424).

References

- Abdel-Monem, A., Watkins, N.D., Gast, P.W., 1972. Potassium-argon ages, volcanic stratigraphy, and geomagnetic polarity history of the Canary Islands; Tenerife, La Palma and Hierro. *Am. J. Sci.* 272, 805–825.
- Anderson, M.P., Woessner, W.W., Hunt, R.J., 2015. *Applied Groundwater Modeling: Simulation of Flow and Advective Transport*. Elsevier Science.
- Becerril, L., Galindo, I., Martí, J., Gudmundsson, A., 2015. Three-armed rifts or masked radial pattern of eruptive fissures? The intriguing case of *El Hierro* volcano (Canary Islands). *Tectonophysics* 647–648, 33–47.
- Bonforte, A., Martí, J., Paonita, A., Pichavant, M., 2022. Editorial: volcanic islands—a challenge for volcanology. *Front. Earth Sci.* 10.
- Burrough, P.A., McDonnell, R.A., Lloyd, C.D., 2015. *Principles of Geographical Information Systems*. Oxford university press.
- Calcagno, P., Chilès, J.-P., Courrioux, G., Guillen, A., 2008. Geological modelling from field data and geological knowledge: Part I. Modelling method coupling 3D potential-field interpolation and geological rules. *Phys. Earth Planet. In.* 171, 147–157.
- Carracedo, J.C., Badiola, E.R., Guillou, H., de la Nuez, J., Torrado, F.P., 2001. Geology and volcanology of *la Palma* and *el Hierro*, western Canaries. *Estudios Geológicos-Madrid* 57, 175–273.
- Cas, R.A., Giordano, G., Wright, J.V., 2018. *Volcanology: Processes, Deposits, Geology and Resources*. Springer International Publishing.
- Comte, J.-C., Cassidy, R., Obando, J., Robins, N., Ibrahim, K., Melchioly, S., et al., 2016. Challenges in groundwater resource management in coastal aquifers of East Africa: investigations and lessons learnt in the Comoros Islands, Kenya and Tanzania. *J. Hydrol.: Reg. Stud.* 5, 179–199.
- Custodio, E., 2020. Hydrogeology and Groundwater Resources in Volcanic Formations and Islands. *Universidad Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona*.
- Custodio, E., Cabrera, MdC., Poncela, R., Puga, L.-O., Skupien, E., del Villar, A., 2016. Groundwater intensive exploitation and mining in *Gran Canaria* and *Tenerife*, Canary Islands, Spain: hydrogeological, environmental, economic and social aspects. *Sci. Total Environ.* 557–558, 425–437.
- Dehotin, J., Braud, I., 2008. Which spatial discretization for distributed hydrological models? Proposition of a methodology and illustration for medium to large-scale catchments. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 12, 769–796.
- Duncan, D., 2012. Freshwater under threat: pacific islands. In: *Vulnerability Assessment of Freshwater Resources to Environmental Change Regional Office for Asia and the Pacific*, Bangkok, p. 66.
- Eamus, D., Fu, B., Springer, A.E., Stevens, L.E., 2016. Groundwater dependent ecosystems: classification, identification techniques and threats. In: Jakeman, A.J., Barreteau, O., Hunt, R.J., Rinaudo, J.-D., Ross, A. (Eds.), *Integrated Groundwater Management: Concepts, Approaches and Challenges*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 313–346.
- El-Rayes, A., Omran, A., Geriash, M., Hochschild, V., 2020. Estimation of hydraulic conductivity in fractured crystalline aquifers using remote sensing and field data analyses: an example from *Wadi Nasab* area, South Sinai, Egypt. *J. Earth Syst. Sci.* 129, 203.
- Elsworth, D., Voight, B., 1995. Dike intrusion as a trigger for large earthquakes and the failure of volcano flanks. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 100, 6005–6024.
- ESRI, 2011. In: Institute, E.S.R. (Ed.), *ArcGIS Desktop: Release 10*. Redlands, CA.
- Fiske, R., Jackson, E., 1972. Orientation and growth of Hawaiian volcanic rifts: the effect of regional structure and gravitational stresses. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. A. Mathematical and Physical Sciences* 329, 299–326.
- Fúster, J.M., F. H., Cendrero, A., Coello, J., Canragrel, J.M., Ancochea, E., et al., 1993. Geocronología de la isla de *El Hierro* (Islas Canarias). *Bol. R. Soc. Esp. Hist. Nat.* 88, 85–97.
- García-Gil, A., Fontes, J.C., Santamarta, J.C., 2022. Groundwater conditions the effectiveness of surface water diversion in the remediation of the eutrophicated volcanic lake of *Furnas*, Azores archipelago. *Sci. Total Environ.* 837, 1575789.
- García-Gil, A., Poncela Poncela, R., Skupien Balon, E., Morales González-Moro, Á., Lario-Báscones, R.J., Marazuela, M.A., Cruz-Pérez, N., Santamarta, J.C., 2022.

- Heterogeneity-Driven Hydrodynamics Conditions the Hydrochemistry of Spring Water in Volcanic Islands. *Groundwater* 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwat.13249>.
- Gee, M.J.R., Masson, D.G., Watts, A.B., Mitchell, N.C., 2001. Offshore continuation of volcanic rift zones, el Hierro, Canary islands. *J. Volcanol. Geoth. Res.* 105, 107–119.
- Gibson, H., Sumpton, J., Fitzgerald, D., Seikel, R., 2013. 3D Modelling of Geology and Gravity Data: Summary Workflows for Minerals Exploration. East Asia: Geology. Exploration Technologies and Mines, pp. 24–26.
- Gill, B., Cherry, D., Adelana, M., Cheng, X., Reid, M., 2011. Using three-dimensional geological mapping methods to inform sustainable groundwater development in a volcanic landscape, Victoria, Australia. *Hydrogeol. J.* 19, 1349–1365.
- Gleeson, T., Cuthbert, M., Ferguson, G., Perrone, D., 2020. Global groundwater sustainability. Resources, and Systems in the Anthropocene 48, 431–463.
- Guillou, H., Carracedo, J.C., Torrado, F.P., Badiola, E.R., 1996. K-Ar ages and magnetic stratigraphy of a hotspot-induced, fast grown oceanic island: el Hierro, Canary Islands. *J. Volcanol. Geoth. Res.* 73, 141–155.
- Hemmings, B., Whitaker, F., Gottsmann, J., Hughes, A., 2015. Hydrogeology of Montserrat review and new insights. *J. Hydrol. Reg. Stud.* 3, 1–30.
- Herrera, C., Custodio, E., 2014. Groundwater flow in a relatively old oceanic volcanic island: the Betancuria area, Fuerteventura Island, Canary Islands, Spain. *Sci. Total Environ.* 496, 531–550.
- Holcomb, R.T., Searle, R.C., 1991. Large landslides from oceanic volcanoes. *Mar. Geotechnol.* 10, 19–32.
- Hughes, J., Petheram, C., Taylor, A., Raiber, M., Davies, P., Levick, S., 2022. Water balance of a small island experiencing climate change. *Water* 14, 1771.
- IGME, 1997a. Sheet and Report N° 1105-II Isla de El Hierro - Valverde. MAGNA. Geological Survey of Spain, Madrid.
- IGME, 1997b. Sheet and Report N° 1105-III Isla de El Hierro - Sabinosa. MAGNA. Geological Survey of Spain, Madrid.
- IGME, 1997c. Sheet and Report N° 1105-IV Isla de El Hierro - Frontera. MAGNA. Geological Survey of Spain, Madrid.
- IGME, 1997d. Sheet and Report N° 1108-II/I Isla de El Hierro - La Restinga. MAGNA. Geological Survey of Spain, Madrid.
- Join, J.-L., Folio, J.-L., Bourhane, A., Comte, J.-C., 2016. Groundwater resources on active basaltic volcanoes: conceptual models from La Réunion island and grande comore. In: Bachelery, P., Lenat, J.-F., Di Muro, A., Michon, L. (Eds.), *Active Volcanoes of the Southwest Indian Ocean: Piton de la Fournaise and Karthala*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 61–70.
- Jurado, M.J., Ripepe, M., Lopez, C., Ricciardi, A., Blanco, M.J., Lacanna, G., 2020. Underwater records of submarine volcanic activity: el Hierro (Canary Islands 2011–2012) eruption. *J. Volcanol. Geoth. Res.* 408, 107097.
- Lachassagne, P., Aunay, B., Frissant, N., Guilbert, M., Malard, A., 2014. High-resolution conceptual hydrogeological model of complex basaltic volcanic islands: a Mayotte, Comoros, case study. *Terra. Nova* 26, 307–321.
- Lajaunie, C., Courrioux, G., Manuel, L., 1997. Foliation fields and 3D cartography in geology: principles of a method based on potential interpolation. *Math. Geol.* 29, 571–584.
- Lopes, D., Barbosa, S., Cruz-Pérez, N., García-Gil, A., Marazuela, M.Á., Rodríguez-Alcántara, J.S., et al., 2022. Excess of naturally occurring fluoride in groundwater discharge in Macaronesia: brava island. Cape Verde. *Water*. 14.
- MacCormack, K., Berg, R., Kessler, H., Russell, H., Thorleifson, L., 2019. Synopsis of Three-Dimensional Geological Mapping and Modelling at Geological Survey Organizations. Alberta Energy Regulator/Alberta Geological Survey, 2019.
- Macdonald, G.A., Abbott, A., Peterson, F.L., 1983. *Volcanoes in the Sea: the Geology of Hawaii*. University of Hawaii press.
- Manconi, A., Longpré, M.-A., Walter, T.R., Troll, V.R., Hansteen, T.H., 2009. The effects of flank collapses on volcano plumbing systems. *Geology* 37, 1099–1102.
- Margat, J., Van der Gun, J., 2013. *Groundwater Around the World: a Geographic Synopsis*. Crc Press.
- Masson, D., Watts, A., Gee, M., Urgeles, R., Mitchell, N., Le Bas, T., et al., 2002. Slope failures on the flanks of the western Canary Islands. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 57, 1–35.
- Morris, B.L., Lawrence, A.R., Chilton, P., Adams, B., Calow, R.C., Klinck, B.A., 2003. Groundwater and its Susceptibility to Degradation: a Global Assessment of the Problem and Options for Management.
- Nugraha, R.P., O'Sullivan, J., 2019. A key process of natural state modeling: 3D Geological model of Jaboi Geothermal field, Nangro Aceh Darussalam, Indonesia. *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 254, 012024.
- Perez-Torrado, F., Rodriguez-Gonzalez, A., Carracedo, J., Fernandez-Turiel, J.L., Guillou, H., Hansen, A., et al., 2011. Edades C-14 Del Rift ONO de El Hierro (Islas Canarias).
- Poncela, R., Santamarta, J.C., García-Gil, A., Cruz-Pérez, N., Skupien, E., García-Barba, J., 2022. Hydrogeological characterization of heterogeneous volcanic aquifers in the Canary Islands using recession analysis of deep water gallery discharge. *J. Hydrol.* 610, 127975.
- Povinec, P.P., Burnett, W.C., Beck, A., Bokuniewicz, H., Charette, M., Gonneea, M.E., et al., 2012. Isotopic, geophysical and biogeochemical investigation of submarine groundwater discharge: IAEA-UNESCO intercomparison exercise at Mauritius Island. *J. Environ. Radioact.* 104, 24–45.
- Prada, S., Silva, M., Cruz, J.V., 2005. Groundwater behaviour in Madeira, volcanic island (Portugal). *Hydrogeol. J.* 13, 800–812.
- Santamarta, J.C., 2017. *Tratado de Minería de Recursos Hídricos en Islas Volcánicas Océánicas*. Sevilla.
- Santamarta, J.C., Rodríguez-Martín, J., 2020. Los procesos de planificación hidrológica en la península ibérica e islas en un contexto de cambio climático. *Colegio Oficial de Ingenieros de Montes, Madrid*.
- Santamarta, J.C., Lario-Bascones, R.J., Rodríguez-Martín, J., Hernández-Gutiérrez, L.E., Poncela, R., 2014. Introduction to hydrology of volcanic islands. *IERI Procedia* 9, 135–140.
- Scanlon, B.R., Keese, K.E., Flint, A.L., Flint, L.E., Gaye, C.B., Edmunds, W.M., et al., 2006. Global Synthesis of Groundwater Recharge in Semiarid and Arid Regions, pp. 3335–3370, 20.
- Schmincke, H.-U., 2004. *Volcanism*, vol. 28. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Siebert, S., Burke, J., Faures, J.-M., Frenken, K., Hoogeveen, J., Döll, P., et al., 2010. Groundwater Use for Irrigation—A Global Inventory, pp. 1863–1880, 14.
- Singhal, B., Gupta, R., 2010. *Hydrogeology of Volcanic Rocks*.
- Székely, N., Laj, C., Guillou, H., Kissel, C., Mazaud, A., Carracedo, J.-C., 1999. Geomagnetic paleosecular variation in the Brunhes period, from the island of el Hierro (canary islands). *Earth Planet Sci. Lett.* 165, 241–253.
- Tribble, G., 2008. Ground Water on Tropical Pacific Islands—Understanding a Vital Resource, p. 35.
- Troll, V.R., Carracedo, J.C., 2016. Chapter 2 - the geology of el Hierro. In: Troll, V.R., Carracedo, J.C. (Eds.), *The Geology of the Canary Islands*. Elsevier, pp. 43–99.
- Turner, A.K., Kessler, H., van der Meulen, M.J., 2021. *Applied Multidimensional Geological Modeling: Informing Sustainable Human Interactions with the Shallow Subsurface*. Wiley.
- Violette, S., d'Ozouville, N., Pryet, A., Defontaine, B., Fortin, J., Adelinet, M., 2014. Hydrogeology of the Galápagos Archipelago. *The Galápagos*, pp. 167–183.
- White, I., Falkland, T., 2010. Management of freshwater lenses on small Pacific islands. *Hydrogeol. J.* 18, 227–246.